

LIMITING AND SUPPORTING FACTORS FOR SCHOOL TO IMPLEMENT SOCIAL INCLUSIVE SCHOOL PROGRAMS: A POLICY ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

There is important task which faced by public and private schools to help a population of children with disabilities through inclusive education. School as education institution has formal and informal rules to support the inclusive education. There is a trend of inclusive social services to be given for children with special needs. As the school is a group of people who have the same goals and motives, school must achieve their interests through institutional structure of formal rules (law, regulation, contract, constitutional law) and informal rules (ethics, beliefs, and other unwritten norms). However, school faced with limiting and supporting factors in the implementation of inclusive program. This paper describes the school efforts and comparing the policy of social inclusive education services in Indonesia. The school must analyze their inclusive program and the education paradigm through social theory, economic ownership and transaction costs and the efficiency of resources and incentive structures. This study concluded that social inclusive education services policies in Indonesia at informal role, which are traditions, norms, customs, religions, school are at productive level, whereas, at formal roles, school must have embedded culture as the behavioral mindset of decentralized actors to create low cost education program. Finally, this study suggested for the Indonesian education administrator to maintain local wisdom and formal rules to strengthen social inclusive education services.

Keywords: *inclusive school policy, policy evaluation, children with special needs*

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1. INTRODUCTION

There is important task which faced by public and private schools to help a population of children with disabilities in Indonesia. A population census data in 2012 reported that 3317 people in every district in Indonesia needs inclusive school which increased 9.2% per annum of average children with physical limitations and disabilities(Haryono,2016). As intellectual, mental and psychiatric limitations are getting increased, there is disabilities rate at national level reached by 12% (Reichman, et al.,2008). At that time, children with special needs are characterized by mainly functional impairment prevalence of 15.5% and disability of 14.1% (Autor, D. H., & Duggan, 2003). This problem is getting serious till now which have an increased trend to 2020. This means that both school and government need clear clarity of the school function into social accountability by accepting the children into social inclusive education services through inter-agency transaction contracts.

It needs school role in education to develop their involvement in education for all paradigms where school must provide strong foundation. However, there is lack of resources for school especially for their policy especially in the school curriculum as an educational design (Kirschner, et al., 2006). Even though curriculum has a very strategic position in all aspects of educational activities, however the importance of the curriculum needs cornerstone of curriculum developer to understand the basis of consideration by education implementers especially school administrators and teachers to be instrumental in conducting coaching and support their community especially for children with special needs (Hasazi, et al., 1994). However, from the perspective of microeconomic theory, to provide social

inclusive education service is still being captured by economic principles, such as economies of scale, economic scope, complementarity, and externalities of institutional matrix networks (Rauniyar, G., & Kanbur, 2010). Public expenditure and capital expenditure are powered by economies of scale. This means that provision of school program has forced school to create efficient public services and mitigation of negative externalities impact. Some scholar argued that the issue is limiting the school to implement program of social inclusive education services (Lipsky, D. K., & Gartner, A., 1996; Van Reusen et al.,2000; Hunt, P., & Goetz, 1997; Fuchs, D., & Fuchs, 1994).

Some scholar also supported the argument that the preparation and development of the curriculum with strong foundations can facilitate the achievement of education for all with effectively and efficiently (Peacock,2001; Tsui, 2007; Thornton, et al,2004). This study provides information about how school administrators can deal with hybrid curriculum development and inclusive education policy. It also identifies some curriculum foundations that should be the basis for inclusive educational policy makers, both at central and regional levels in conducting educational planning for the children with special needs. It observes how school can apply curriculum program with optimal value for the children.

Basically, assistance for disabled children care needs disseminating aid program for disabled person for living in social institution. However, there is limitation for the assistance especially it only covers basic needs such as food and shelter. There is lack of information about how the children with special needs will get adequate education. As Indonesia has 137 districts, there is wide area and challenge for policy directors and disable

care program to provide education and social services besides education service of children with disabilities.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

School as social awareness institution

As school is institution with increasing social awareness of the community, school has main role in utilizing the potential and sources of social welfare and economic resources for the development of education program (Duncan, G. J., & Brooks-Gunn, 2000; DiNitto, D. M., & Johnson, 2015). However, school also lack of economic resources to provide education service into adequate level of life quality and social welfare; therefore, school must have policy direction even though it also needs school ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Children with Disabilities and the issuance of regulations that provide education as rights of children with disabilities (Kayess, R., & French, 2008).

School and government are the main example of principal-agent relationships (Miller, 2005). Accountability pathways have ranged from school with their government through no-performance contracts, and no reward and punishment mechanisms. Community has limited information (bounded rationality) of choosing school with limited supervision to perform accountability. It drives school to provide only average performance and agreement between the two parties that does not benefit the public interest.

Cooperation between schools with Ministry of Social Service is also encouraged. However, the expansion of social services and education service services to children with disabilities has lack of information about the policy to involve social services professional into school institution. In addition, the social education service for children with

disabilities is still based on social work field, it rarely explores the role of teacher, school administrator, and curriculum developer to understand deeply their role to help children with disabilities (Adelman, H. S., & Taylor, 1993; Field, 1996).

There is a trend to strengthen the school management of social education service of children with disabilities. However, it needs social inclusive education services policies in the implementation of public governance by considering the uniqueness of diverse social and cultural values of the regions and prioritizing the potential and social resources of families and local communities in the service and social education service for the children (Milbourne, 2002). Even though the responsibilities of providing educational service to the children is taken by school and local schools, however, the involvement of communities in the provision of social education services to children with disabilities has become main issues especially about the advocacy and social assistance in the management of social services and education service programs and welfare of children with disabilities (Ainscow, et al., 2000. This has been explained in the direction of policies and programs and social services and education service activities in the PRJMN 2010-2014 that promoting education service as part of equitable social services is getting important.

Even though, it has been promoted in the National Action Plan for Disabled Children 2004-2013, there are lack resources especially human resources aspects in education service in handling problems and potentials of management in terms of planning, implementing, monitoring, evaluating and reporting and coordination. In addition, many schools also lack of resource in creating a climate

and system that promotes development of community participation for children with disabilities. In addition, the delivery of social education service also has barrier in the degree of disability, recognition of social cultural values, potential priority and source of family and local community (Barnes, C., & Mercer, 2005). It means that providing such service is the problem of multi-sectorial ministries and schools of children with disabilities including middle school and universities to build National Coordinating Team for implementing and study the disability social welfare programs mentioned above.

Following United Nation Ratification on Human Rights of Children with Disabilities, since 30 March 2007 Indonesia has been a signatory to the Convention on the Rights of Children with Disabilities (CRPD). Currently Indonesia is in the process of ratification, and in 2011 the Indonesian Government has submitted to Parliament. In addition, in adapting the paradigm change of disability from the welfare approach to the fulfillment of the human rights paradigm, the school has also conducted a review of disability terminology which has been used in daily communication as well as officially declared in the state document. Officially, the term 'people with disabilities' are substitute for the term 'children with disabilities'. The paradigm is then expanded to the school curriculum specially to support the law ratification.

It impacts the institutional framework of social inclusive education services policy is not optimal in forming an incentive structure to provide skills and knowledge for children with special needs. The school as framework of social inclusive education services has not produced maximum outcomes to support the services.

School role and policies in social inclusive education services

During the past five years, the school developed comprehensive legislation that governs the responsibilities and obligations of central school, provincial, and local levels and stakeholders at the community level in the provision of education services. The development planning of the education sector is prepared on the basis of the legal obligations of the state as described in the Fourth Amendment of the 1945 Constitution on the provision of educational services (art. 31), Law no. 17/2003 on State Finances, Law no. 20/2003 on National Education System, Law no. 25/2004 on National Development Planning System, Law no. 32/2004 on Regional School, Law no. 33/2004 on the Fiscal Balance between Central and Regional Schools, and Law no. 14/2005 on Teachers and Lecturers.

The law mandates the implementation of education social inclusive education services in two phases, namely the transfer of authority to administer education services from the central school to local schools and (ii) submissions from the Ministry of National Education to the schools as the application of school-based management. Meanwhile, the law mandates a greater role for the community to engage in education boards at the local level and school committees at the individual school level (Tomasevski, 2003). School is legitimate to provide services and improving the quality and relevance of education as required by Law no. 20/2003 on the National Education System. It is also stated in detail by School Regulation no. 19/2005 on National Education Standards to recognize human rights in a broad sense including in social inclusive education services.

The social inclusive education services of central school administrative

authority to the local level means that regions have greater authority to apply, greater freedom in decision-making, and more to reflect the needs of local communities to better serve the social needs and development of local communities (Alexiadou, N., & Ozga, 2002).

Based of Law no. 14 on the increased in functional allowance, school has higher budget allocation for their professional role in working in remote areas. In the past, when teachers were assigned to remote areas, the education of their children relied heavily on existing educational facilities in these remote areas. Given its low income, most teachers do not have the economic capacity to fund the continued education of their children outside the region. From the point of view of human rights, this is a form of respect for the rights of teachers and their families, including the rights of their children's education.

Human Rights and Civic Education

The 2003 Education Law sets the juridical foundation to ensure advantaged and disadvantaged groups get the full attention from school especially from school. Particular attention to fair education service is directed to: (i) minority groups of language, religion and ethnicity; (ii) socioeconomic classes and various stratifications, (iii) gender; (iv) special needs children: (v) remote villagers, and residents located in far islands and border areas; and (vi) poor children, orphans, street children and child laborers (Mitchell, B. M., & Salsbury, 1996).

Children of minority groups, children living in remote areas, children living in rural areas, and marginalized children are grouped into groups of underserved children by their educational needs (Weber, 2014). Kemendiknas is then

adopted a new strategy to bring education services to children who have not been served. The strategy has four steps: (i) recognize their characteristics, (ii) understanding their educational needs; (iii) finding out inclusive education system.

The educational needs provision using existing shape or develop new alternatives if needed. Human rights education and education as a human right can be seen as two sides of a coin. Indonesia provides education with human rights using the point of view of Education for All (EFA). EFA mandates adoption of targets in six areas, namely: early childhood education, primary education, literacy education, life skills cultivation, gender equality, and quality education. The first four areas can be viewed as areas schools with their goals and targets, while the other two are the principles that support the other four areas. the school achievements in providing educational services is as a fulfillment of human rights using the EFA point of view.

Role of government and school in the student performance

To achieve quality education, the school adopted three strategies to improve quality(Sallis,2014). The first strategy is to improve student and school performance by strengthening the examination system for students and school accreditation, developing institutions that set standards and strengthen national and sub-national capabilities in implementing these systems. The second strategy is to increase the availability of key quality-oriented inputs through setting minimum standards for such inputs and making financial and management reference for the provision of those inputs. The third strategy is to strengthen the quality control system and capacity building capabilities. Overall student performance

as indicated by the average scores of national graduation exams that increased significantly in junior and senior secondary schools. Furthermore, progress Ministry of National Education which meaning that social inclusive service must be included in the standards and accreditation for schools. Minimum standards for school performance were created and disseminated in 2004 and the capacity to handle school performance accreditation has been expanded through the School Accreditation Board and provincial / regional accreditation and supervisory systems. Approximately 53 percent of educational institutions have been formally accredited at present. However, there is lack of information about how many school have implemented inclusive program in their curriculum.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research conducted is a policy research by using the policy research approach model that is by referring to the rules of policy research (Ozga, 1999). In order to obtain comprehensive information, this study follows the following stages: (1) create a research design that describes the flow of research, (2) define and describe the important variables that will be studied in detail and techniques to obtain data, (3) data collection methods, (4) sampling methods, (5) data analysis techniques, (6) research time, and (7) personal observations.

The problem studied in this study is to identify some of the strategic and implementation policies that have been and are being made by the city / county school in Jakarta province that is focused provision of inclusive program by school in Jakarta. Furthermore, important aspects are incorporated into the policy analysis procedure. Therefore, the research variables for obtaining accurate data are

as identifying the problem to be solved and justification of the accuracy of the policy formulation that has been formulated on the basis of the problems faced. It finally evaluates the policies implemented both at national and local level school efforts in the implementation of the program and provide alternative to overcome the problems faced.

Observation activities were conducted in 4 schools of inclusive education providers, while interviews were conducted on 6 students with special needs and 3 parents of students with special needs. More details on this can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Object Observations and Interview Informants in Inclusive Schools

Province	District/ City	School of Inclusive Education Organizer	Number of Specific Needed Educational Participants	Number of Special Needed Educative Participants Interviewed	Number of Parents / Guardians of Students with Special Needs interviewed	Type of Specificity
DKI Jakarta	Jakarta Pusat	SD Cempaka Putih Barat 16	1		1	Low TunaVision Grahita
		SD Johar Baru 29	1		1	Deaf
	Jakarta Utara	SD Marunda 02	1	1		CP/Tuna Daksa
			1	1		Learning Difficulties
		SD Kelapa Gading 04	1	1		Autism
		1		1	Autism	
Total			6	3	3	

4. ANALYSIS RESULT

Analysis and interpretation of data is done based on the type of information sources obtained. This information then integrated with each other so that the information obtained especially on the Allocation Function as the basis of policy.

Table 2. Policy Recommendation

Issue	Findings (Research Result)	Policy Suggestions
Children do not go to school	High in underdeveloped areas	Improved implementation of Community Support System
	Due to economic and non-economic factors	
Children drop out	Low access of vulnerable children	Increased access to inclusive education services
	Many occur in children prone to DO	Intervention of teachers to handle children prone to DO
Children's Learning Difficulties	Due to economic and economic factors	Cooperation with PT for prospective teachers who are competent and placed in disadvantaged areas
		An intensive 9 years of intensive socialization
Children's Learning Difficulties	Children's learning difficulties benefit from learning to use ICT	Utilization of ICT in learning process
Reproduction in adolescent girls	The integrated health outreach model of adolescent health has a positive impact on social, medical, and psychosocial health.	School involvement in PTKR

According to Williamson, C. R. (2009), institutions are formal rules and informal rules and their enforcement rules. While the school is a group of people (players) who have the same goals and motives. Schools and schools achieve their interests in an institutional structure of formal rules (law, regulation, contract, constitutional law) and informal rules (ethics, beliefs, and other unwritten norms). The school then has internal rules to deal with personnel issues, budgets, procurement and reporting procedures, which limit the implementation of inclusive program. Thus, institutions are an incentive structure for school and individual behavior. The policy of social inclusive education services in Indonesia from 1974, 1999 and 2004 bring institutional change of patterns of exchange of authority (exchange). Another economic Nobel Prize, Williamson in 2000, argued that institutions are divided into four mutually reciprocal levels. Starting with level I is social theory (social theory) which is school has informal role which inherent in society, such as tradition, norm, custom, and convention. Level II emphasizes the economic ownership (economics of property right) which consists of legal institutions, and bureaucracy. Level III emphasizes transaction costs (transaction cost economics) which exchange their resources with community. Level IV emphasizes the efficiency of resources and incentive structures. Based on North (1990) and Williamson (2000) school has actively involved in the social inclusive education services policies in Indonesia. At informal role, which are traditions, norms, customs, religions, school are the productive and non-productive habits which incompatible in favor of formal roles. At second level, school must be embedded culture as the behavioral mindset of decentralized actors to create

low cost education program. In addition, the Indonesian education administration has been influenced by the traditional concept of power and hierarchy, which emphasizes the centralization of power, patrimonial behavior, and top-down decision making in school program (McLaughlin, M. W., & Marsh, 1990). In this level, school must maintain local wisdom in order to be compatible with formal rules that can strengthen social inclusive education services.

Comparing the system of rules contained in Law no. 32/2004 and clarified in School Regulation no. 38/2007 the division of authority has not yet provided a clear clarity of function. The authority system is divided hierarchically, in which the central authority is monetary, trade, religious, defense and military, while other authorities are shared between central, provincial and district and municipal schools based on accountability, efficiency and impact of externalities (Kristiansen, S., & Trijono, 2005). Uncertainty occurs either vertically or horizontally, causing uncertainty over the ownership rights of central, provincial and local schools, the unclear contract of ownership relations. In addition, sectorial ego and multi-stakeholder authority at the central level are still occurring, which also result in multiple interpretations of authority ownership at provincial and district and municipal levels. In addition, there is a vagueness of formal ownership with informality such as customary property rights, traditions as in the case of land; plantations, forestry and mining. Moreover, the unclear division of authority also as a result of delays in ministries and agencies in the central school prepare the Standard Procedures and Criteria. At third level, school must work like other organization to maintain their budget and resource. It needs a bounded rationality and opportunistic

behavior that increased transaction cost economics. The policy of social inclusive education services has shifted the pattern of monopoly and discretion into social accountability by accepting the children into social inclusive education services through inter-agency transaction contracts (Arnesen, A. L., & Lundahl, 2006).

Fourth, the model mental constructs of the actors of social inclusive education services have not changed. From the perspective of microeconomic theory, social inclusive education services policy has still been captured by economic principles, such as economies of scale, economic scope, complementarity, and externalities of institutional matrix networks (Rafiqui, 2008). Public expenditure and capital expenditure are powered by economies of scale. Or in other words, long-term average spending increases steadily, which is not followed by an increase in the output of school program, has forced school to create efficient public services and mitigation of negative externalities impact. It limited the school to implement program of social inclusive education services.

It also impacts on the vertical accountability to horizontal accountability and return to vertical accountability has led to a lack of clarity on principal-agent relationships. Accountability pathways ranged from school with their community through no-performance contracts, and no reward and punishment mechanisms. Community has limited information (bounded rationality) of choosing school with limited supervision to perform accountability. It drives school to provide only low performance and agreement between the two parties that does not benefit the public interest.

Seventh, the institutional framework of social inclusive education services policy is not optimal in forming an incentive structure to provide skills

and knowledge for their students (e.g., the children with special needs). It is considered to provide low maximum pay-off. The design of social inclusive education services policy in Indonesia is incomplete, there is no clear ownership of authority, performance contract, no meritocracy system, and no functional office certification for local school management actors, it can be said that the school as framework of social inclusive education services has not produced maximum outcomes to support the services. Uncompetitive environments have not encouraged schools to invest in skills and knowledge and have not shaped the perception of institutional change to be more efficient and effective (Boyd, 1992).

Eighth, Law no. 32 of 2004 on Regional School and school regulation or PP no. 41 (2007) and Regulation Number 57 of 2007 are still nuanced centralist. Schools are established on the basis of authority, population, area and amount of APBD. Schools are not created on the basis of competence, bottom up based on perceptions of human resource skills, spatial conditions and economic potential of each region. In addition to the many positive evidences that can be found as a result of social inclusive education services policies, the above description still leaves some complexity of problems such as unclear institutional and institutional governance such as uncertainty contracts of political, administrative and fiscal authority relationships, lack of clarity of principal-agent relationships and lack of clarity of incentive structures and weak control and enforcement of civil society and ultimately led to increased costs of economic transactions.

As education paradigm has influenced the change of the institutional system of social inclusive education services in Indonesia, Indonesia needs a

strong alignment of a formal and informal set of rules and its enforcers to create a structure of incentive mechanisms both the central and regional levels in order to lower educational budgeting costs. The institutional arrangements for efficient governance in social inclusive education services in Indonesia must be based on hybrid macro-institutional environment of formal Law no. 32/2004 on School and Law no. 33/2004 on Regional Financial Balance, Law No.25 / 2004 on Regional Planning, Law No.1 of 2004, Law No.17 of 2003 on State Finance, Law No.15 of 2004 on Supervision of State Financial Management and a set of informal rules. Delegation of authority to the school is important in order the school to be close to the people. Local wisdom or social capital such as; social networks, village assemblies, adapt sanctions, norms, agreements, religions that were once separate from the legal framework or the de-coupling institutions should be incorporated into the formal rules to support the program of social inclusive education services.

Conclusion

On the level of concept and praxis, efficient institutional economic design needs to be undertaken in the future social inclusive education services in Indonesia. Efficient institutional design in question is the design that is not only pro community but also the pro local wisdom. The paradigm shift of the twentieth-century school which characterized by unity, centralized, bureaucratic, guided and controlled, risk-intolerant, closed and slow, depending must be reformed to be instruction of confederation, participatory, globalizing and localized, participatory, responsive and accountable, risk-tolerant, open-minded and fast-competitive competence.

Other supporting elements that should be considered in the preparation of this step strategy are: (i) school restructuring and human resources based on competence oriented to public services, and promotion of inter-regional and private cooperation contracts in the provision of social inclusive services; (v) enhanced supervision and coordination including improvement of incentive mechanism and stimulus for social inclusive education services.

References

- Adelman, H. S., & Taylor, L. (1993). *Learning Problems & Learning Disabilities: Moving Forward*. Brooks/Cole Publishing Company, 511 Forest Lodge Rd., Pacific Grove, CA 93950-5098.
- Ainscow, M., Farrell, P., & Tweddle, D. (2000). Developing policies for inclusive education: a study of the role of local education authorities. *International journal of inclusive education*, 4(3), 211-229.
- Alexiadou, N., & Ozga, J. (2002). Modernising education governance in England and Scotland: devolution and control. *European Educational Research Journal*, 1(4), 676-691.
- Arnesen, A. L., & Lundahl, L. (2006). Still social and democratic? Inclusive education policies in the Nordic welfare states. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 50(3), 285-300.
- Autor, D. H., & Duggan, M. G. (2003). The rise in the disability rolls and the decline in unemployment. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(1), 157-206.
- Barnes, C., & Mercer, G. (2005). Disability, work, and welfare: challenging the social exclusion of disabled people. *Work, employment and society*, 19(3), 527-545.

- Boyd, V. (1992). School Context: Bridge or Barrier for Change?.
- DiNitto, D. M., & Johnson, D. H. (2015). Social welfare: Politics and public policy. Pearson.
- Duncan, G. J., & Brooks-Gunn, J. (2000). Family poverty, welfare reform, and child development. *Child development*, 71(1), 188-196.
- Field, S. (1996). Self-determination instructional strategies for youth with learning disabilities. *Journal of learning disabilities*, 29(1), 40-52.
- Fuchs, D., & Fuchs, L. S. (1994). Inclusive schools movement and the radicalization of special education reform. *Exceptional children*, 60(4), 294-309.
- Haryono, G. N. (2016). Studi Evaluasi Program Pendidikan Inklusif Bagi Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus di Sekolah Dasar Kabupaten Pontianak.
- Hasazi, S. B., Johnston, A. P., Liggett, A. M., & Schattman, R. A. (1994). A qualitative policy study of the least restrictive environment provision of the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act. *Exceptional Children*, 60(6), 491-507.
- Hunt, P., & Goetz, L. (1997). Research on inclusive educational programs, practices, and outcomes for students with severe disabilities. *The Journal of Special Education*, 31(1), 3-29.
- Kayess, R., & French, P. (2008). Out of darkness into light? Introducing the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. *Human rights law review*, 8(1), 1-34.
- Kirschner, P. A., Sweller, J., & Clark, R. E. (2006). Why minimal guidance during instruction does not work: An analysis of the failure of constructivist, discovery, problem-based, experiential, and inquiry-based teaching. *Educational psychologist*, 41(2), 75-86.
- Kristiansen, S., & Trijono, L. (2005). Authority and law enforcement: local government reforms and security systems in Indonesia. *Contemporary Southeast Asia*, 236-254.
- Lipsky, D. K., & Gartner, A. (1996). Inclusion, school restructuring, and the remaking of American society. *Harvard Educational Review*, 66(4), 762-797.
- McLaughlin, M. W., & Marsh, D. D. (1990). Staff development and school change. *Schools as collaborative cultures: Creating the future now*, 213-232.
- Milbourne, L. (2002). Life at the margin: education of young people, social policy and the meanings of social exclusion. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 6(4), 325-343.
- Miller, G. J. (2005). The political evolution of principal-agent models. *Annu. Rev. Polit. Sci.*, 8, 203-225.
- Mitchell, B. M., & Salsbury, R. E. (1996). *Multicultural education: An international guide to research, policies, and programs*. Greenwood Publishing Group.
- Ozga, J. (1999). *Policy research in educational settings: Contested terrain*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Peacock, J. (2001). Teaching skills for teaching librarians: postcards from the edge of the educational paradigm. *Australian Academic & Research Libraries*, 32(1), 26-42.
- Rafiqui, P. S. (2008). Evolving economic landscapes: why new institutional economics matters for economic geography. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 9(3), 329-353.
- Rauniyar, G., & Kanbur, R. (2010). Inclusive development: Two papers

on conceptualization, application, and the ADB perspective. Manila: Asian Development Bank.

Reichman, N. E., Corman, H., & Noonan, K. (2008). Impact of child disability on the family. *Maternal and child health journal*, 12(6), 679-683.

Sallis, E. (2014). *Total quality management in education*. Routledge.

Thornton, B., Peltier, G., & Perreault, G. (2004). Systems thinking: A skill to improve student achievement. *The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas*, 77(5), 222-230.

Tomasevski, K. (2003). *Education denied: Costs and remedies*. Zed books.

Tsui, L. (2007). Effective strategies to increase diversity in STEM fields: A review of the research literature. *The Journal of Negro Education*, 555-581.

Van Reusen, A. K., Shoho, A. R., & Barker, K. S. (2000). High school teacher attitudes toward inclusion. *The High School Journal*, 84(2), 7-20.

Weber, J. J. (2014). Flexible multilingual education: Putting children's needs first (Vol. 38). *Multilingual Matters*.

Williamson, C. R. (2009). Informal institutions rule: institutional arrangements and economic performance. *Public Choice*, 139(3-4), 371-387.

Williamson, O. E. (2000). The new institutional economics: taking stock, looking ahead. *Journal of economic literature*, 38(3), 595-6